

IMPORTANCE OF ONLINE PROGRAMS IN INCREASING STUDENT'S VOCABULARY

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Annotatsiya: Tadqiqotchilarning fikriga ko'ra, o'quv materialining yuqori informatsion qobiliyatini ta'minlaydigan axborot texnologiyalari va texnik vositalardan foydalanishni o'z ichiga olgan chet tilini (FL), xususan, ingliz tilini (EL) o'qitishning ko'plab usullari mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: mobil ilova, mobil ta'lim, Ingliz lug'atini rivojlantirish, mashqlar, onlayn o'yinlar.

Аннотация: Помнению исследователей, существует множество методов обучения иностранному языку (ИЯ), в частности, английскому языку (АЯ), предполагающих использование информационных технологий и технических средств, которые обеспечивают высокую информативность учебного материала.

Ключевые слова: мобильное приложение; мобильное обучение; развитие английской лексики; упражнения; онлайн-игры.

Annotation: According to the researchers, there are many methods of teaching a foreign language (FL), in particular, English (EL), involving the use of information technologies and technical means that provide a high informative capacity of educational material.

Keywords: mobile app, mobile learning, development of English vocabulary, exercises, online games.

INTRODUCTION

The foundation of oral and written communication in each language is vocabulary. Teaching vocabulary has become a crucial part of learning English as, without it, pupils are unable to comprehend others or articulate their own thoughts, claim Jannah et al. (2020). According to Andi and Arafah (2017), the development of vocabulary and its breadth of knowledge help learners improve their English proficiency, fostering conversation or interaction in the language. Both educators and students understand how crucial vocabulary acquisition is to effective communication in the English language. Nonetheless, little study has been done to find out that learners may find it challenging to pick up new vocabulary in English (Vasileiadou & Makrina, 2017). Teachers must determine the most efficient technique to teach English vocabulary, such as using digital resources, in order to allow students to acquire it in a creative way (Alamr, 2019). The conventional approaches that were added to the present educational programs are among the unsatisfactory methods and techniques that have failed to teach vocabulary in the classroom (Andreani & Ying, 2019). Some studies suggest that using online educational games in the classroom is a useful strategy for teachers looking to introduce vocabulary in a novel way to their English classes (Seli, 2015). Because online games are created in English-speaking nations where English is the primary language, learners pick up English while playing them. Thus, this study examines the effects of teaching English vocabulary to eighth-grade students at Mercedes Vazquez Correa (MVC) through online educational games vs conventional in-class techniques. Additionally, this study looks at how these students feel about learning English vocabulary through traditional techniques and instructional online games.

There are many ways to learn foreign languages. The most common of them are classes with a tutor, studying a standard school or university curriculum, less often self-education. Distance learning for specific languages is also popular. But the aforementioned methods take a lot of time, effort, require a lot of

concentration, sometimes not a small amount of money is required. However, there is a category of people who can easily and simply combine business with pleasure and learn languages in the gameplay.

METHODS

In our time, every person at least once watched films in a foreign language with subtitles, browsed a foreign language site, or simply listened to foreign audio tracks. Definitely, many experienced some inconvenience, but still a certain number of new foreign words were remembered, especially when repeatedly viewing or listening to texts.

There are a significant number of computer programs and applications that increase the effectiveness of the educational process:

- programs developed by the creators of various EUMC, both domestic and foreign (the inclusion of various forms of work with TCO is now a prerequisite for the development of a modern EUMC),
- programs to increase the level of mastering the skills and abilities of individual language components (working out, improving and correcting pronunciation / listening, replenishing the vocabulary with lexical units, consolidating them in permanent memory and introducing them into active vocabulary, as well as studying grammar and error correction with a detailed explanation of the material in online mode),
- entertainment resources (CDs with karaoke songs in the target language, language quests, etc.).

But there is an even easier and more enjoyable way to take your knowledge of foreign languages to the next level. Various single-player and multiplayer online games are very popular nowadays.

RESULTS

Often, single-player games are released only in the original language and have complex storylines, which sometimes require far from basic knowledge of a foreign language to understand. But the desire to understand the plot subconsciously pushes the gamer to search for a translation of unfamiliar words.

As for online games, people from different cities and countries have the opportunity to communicate on various gaming topics, but sometimes the language barrier becomes a serious obstacle to mutual understanding. To solve this problem, people resort to online translators or dictionaries (Google Translate, Bing Translator, Babel Fish, PROMT, Yandex Dictionaries (Lingvo), Multilex, Tweet Translate, etc.), with frequent use of which players remember more and more new word. Since there are foreign multiplayer online games, it happens that you need to communicate with people not only in writing, but also verbally. This, in turn, requires at least a minimum knowledge of a foreign language, and in addition, it perfectly develops spoken language.

However, teachers have identified certain issues with these mobile vocabulary study apps. They highlight how many learning apps these days are commercial in nature, meaning that in order for teachers to utilize the full range of features, they must purchase the yearly subscriptions. Although helpful, this feature presents challenges for some people who are less fortunate. Another issue that teachers who were interviewed may face is their fear that mobile apps may sometimes work against them by diverting students' attention from their academic work.

Teachers, on the other hand, are well aware of this circumstance and make every effort to manage and regulate it in order to maximize the advantages of mobile apps for language learning. The study's findings unequivocally support the beneficial impacts of mobile-assisted language learning through applications on vocabulary instruction and acquisition. The findings appear to be consistent with a study conducted by Davie and Hilber (2015). They came to the conclusion that language learners' motivation might be increased by using smartphone apps like Quizlet.

DISCUSSION

Although this research does not focus on enhancing social contact like KukulskaHulme and Shield (2008), they do have one thing in common: improved student collaboration, which can be demonstrated

through teacher-hosted games or competitions on mobile vocabulary learning apps. Another factor is learner autonomy. This study demonstrated how students at a public university completed vocabulary tests on their phones or when they were given homework assignments that required them to complete the test independently (Oberg & Daniels, 2013).

Globally speaking, mobile learning applications significantly improve vocabulary retention, particularly for challenging terms. More specifically, vocabulary learning through mobile apps can benefit students of all skill levels; language learners may feel more motivated and incentivized to concentrate on their studies, leading to better progress in vocabulary memorization (Chen & Chung, 2008; Lee, 2014; Masrai & Milton, 2015; Kohnke et al., 2019). This study and Mindog (2016) agree that using smartphone applications can help kids improve their spelling and vocabulary as long as they want to use them regularly. "It would seem that participants' inter-mediate language proficiency allows them to focus on understanding the content without worrying too much about individual words or grammar," she writes for the article (p.16). Similarly, mobile vocabulary learning applications show significant and beneficial effects on language learners of mobile-assisted L2 word learning (Lin & Lin, 2019; Le, 2021). These two major factors are congruent with the results of this study. First of all, because mobile applications give teachers and students greater freedom and creativity in their learning, they are better than traditional learning methods.

Second, there is a discernible increase in word retention as a result of using smartphone apps, even while lower-level students still rely more on their teachers than their more engaged and enthusiastic colleagues (Davie & Hilber, 2015; Godwin-Jones, 2011).

The use of computer games makes it much easier, faster and more interesting to learn English, develop memory, attention, imagination, and the ability to find patterns.

One can talk endlessly about the harmful effects of computer games on a person, but they have an undeniable, although not the main advantage: learning foreign languages, thanks to them, becomes more optimal and does not require much concentration of attention and physical and mental costs. The use of computer games in our country is a completely new approach to the educational process. In any case, the introduction of games into the educational process will happen sooner or later, because the younger generation devotes a lot of time to video games, and so that this does not harm the educational process, these two activities must be combined.

So, for example, the introduction of the game "The Sims 3" in the project activity in a foreign language is very effective. A computer game is universal and can be used as a means of self-study of a foreign language or as a TCO directly in a foreign language class (in group tasks to save time).

CONCLUSION

The crucial function that internet apps play in teaching students new vocabulary in the classroom has been reinforced by this study. The author wants to highlight the advantages of using apps to provide new lessons or go over previously taught material for both teachers and students. It outlines the effectiveness, predictability, and motivating elements of using apps to acquire new vocabulary. Students are more likely to become involved in the educational process. However, there are a number of financial issues, and teachers are burdened by the copyrights of these programs.

Therefore, a summary of some pedagogical implications is necessary. First and foremost, teachers should use apps to strategically teach new vocabulary based on the subjects, needs, and proficiency levels of their pupils. Second, even if vocabulary learning applications are helping students more, they still need to be managed or properly guided to avoid getting lost or losing focus. Finally, when teachers figure out how to take advantage of these apps without having to pay more to upgrade their accounts, the basic package of these apps might be streamlined. If not, educators can save money by sharing an account. Additionally, this study's flaws are acknowledged objectively.

The interviews are not sufficiently large to ensure more thorough and impartial outcomes. Some respondents may not recall as much information as they might about their app usage because they were contacted by phone and were not aware of the interview questions beforehand. Therefore, future study should be more thorough. Additionally, more research can be useful in the following areas: a quantitative study on how online apps' design, content, interface, and user-friendliness affect learning performance; and the use of digital devices in the process of learning other productive skills (speaking and writing).

References

1. Ahmadi, M. R. (2018). The Use of Technology in English Language Learning: A literature Review. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 3(2). <http://ijreeonline.com/article-1-120-en.html> (18 April 2020).
2. Aiex, N. K. (1988). *Storytelling by Children*. ERIC Clearinghouse on Reading and Communication Skills Bloomington. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED299574> [5 May 2020].
3. Bland, J. (2013). *Children's Literature and Learner Empowerment: Children and Teenagers in English Language Education*, (1st ed.). New York: Bloomsbury Academy.
4. Cameron, L. (2001). *Teaching Languages to Young Learners*. United Kingdom: Cambridge.
5. Dexter, S.L., Anderson R. E. & Becker H.J. (2014). Teachers' Views of Computers as Catalysts for Changes in Their Teaching Practice. *Journal of Research on Computing in Education*, 3(3): 221-239.
6. Erkaya, R. O. (2005). Benefits of Using Short Stories in the EFL Context. *Asian EFL Journal*. 8:38-49.
7. Erokhina, E.A. Computer technologies as an effective method of teaching a foreign language / E.A. Erokhin // *Open lesson*. 10/25/2017.
8. Malyavina S. V., Shestakov V. V. The use of the computer game "The Sims 3" in the teaching and educational process in a foreign language // *Young scientist*. - 2018. - No. 21. - S. 655-657.
9. Chekun, O. A. Didactic potential of information and communication technologies in teaching foreign languages in higher education. // *Innovative approaches in teaching foreign languages: a collection of scientific articles following the results of the annual scientific seminar*. - M., 2019. - S. 4-9.
10. Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching* (5th ed.). Pearson Education.
11. Chapelle, C. A. (2003). *English Language Learning and Technology: Lectures on Applied Linguistics in the Age of Information and Communication Technology*. John Benjamins Publishing.
12. Doughty, C., & Long, M. (2003). *The Handbook of Second Language Acquisition*. Blackwell Publishing.
13. Ellis, R. (2003). *Task-Based Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford University Press.
14. Krashen, S. D. (1982). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. Pergamon Press.
15. Rosell-Aguilar, F. (2018). Autonomous language learning through a mobile application: a user evaluation of the busuu app. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 31(8), 854–881. <http://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2018.1456465>
16. Stockwell, G. (2010). Using Mobile Phones For Vocabulary Activities: Examining The Effect Of The Platform, 14(2), 95–110. Retrieved from <http://lt.msu.edu/vol14num2/stockwell.pdf>
17. Sweeney, P., & Moore, C. (2013). Mobile Apps for Learning Vocabulary. *International Journal of Computer-Assisted Language Learning and Teaching*, 2(4), 1–16. <http://doi.org/10.4018/ijcallt.2012100101> Wilkinson, D., & Birmingham, P. (2003). *Using Research Instruments : a Guide for Researchers*. London: RoutledgeFalmer.